

Organic Pollutants: Demerits and its green remediation

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There are lots of undesirable end-products in agriculture which has the potential to bio-accumulate. These are also capable of long-range transport. These end products are termed as Organic pollutants. These pollutants are also known as persistent organic pollutants (POPs) such as pesticides and various harmful chemicals. It is accumulated in organisms that lead to undesirable health effects, including infertility and cancer.

Organic pollutants such as dyes are broadly used by many industries such as textile, leather, food, and paper. According to a report given by Mashkooor and Nasar, 2021, Above 7 lakh tons of dyes are produced per annum around the world out of which 20% of these dyes are discharged into water without proper treatment. These dyes are persistent owing to their structural stability. These are carcinogenic, mutagenic and toxic. The dyes obstruct sunlight penetration into the water as a result of which aquatic life suffer. It causes abruption of the photosynthetic process that brings toxicity to aquatic life. Kadhom et al., 2020 asserted that smaller quantities of dyes impart significant colouration to the water that makes it unfit to drink. Apart from dyes, Lapworth et al., 2012 enunciated that organic pollutants such as pharmaceuticals, herbicides pesticides, aromatics, etc. pour into water bodies causing serious health concerns. Thus, it is very important to elucidate a low-cost and eco-friendly strategy to proficiently eradicate these organic pollutants. There are many technologies existed but Dai et al., 2019 suggested for adsorption techniques. This technique use hydrochars from

agro wastes. It has been successfully working as a low-cost and eco-friendly substitute.

Biotic and Abiotic catalysis is used in the degradation of Organic pollutants. Enzymes are biotic catalysts and mineral colloids are abiotic catalysts. But it is a Herculean task to assess the kind of organic pollutants that are being degraded either abiotically or biotically. Important abiotic and biotic catalytic reactions take place simultaneously in the most instances.

The use of extracellular enzymes in the degradation of organic pollutants is broadly accepted. For example, Malathion is hydrolyzed to a monocarboxylic acid through loss of an ethyl group by a carboxyl esterase isolated from soil. Enzymes commonly occurring in soil, such as esterases, amidases, phosphatases, and proteases, catalyze the hydrolysis of the respective chemical bonds in xenobiotic molecules.

Most organic chemicals, including xenobiotics, show a strong affinity to humic substances. However, transformation of xenobiotics in terrestrial systems is greatly influenced by mineral components of soil. Mineral colloids, which are abundant in soil and have large specific surface and relatively high-charge density, contribute to the overall xenobiotic transformation at least as much as does the organic matter.

The application of the plants-endophytic bacteria relationship is a mounting approach for the absolute removal of OPs. Endophytic bacteria are a set of microorganisms that establish their healthy colonies in the plant tissues without causing any impairment to the host plant and show mutualistic relationships with plants. Endophytic bacteria get nutrient and safe habitat from the host plant and in return, it produces several types of growth-promoting substances and bioactive compounds that enhance the degradation of OPs. However, the combined application of plants and endophytic bacteria gives new perceptions to increase phytoremediation potential. Engineered endophytic bacteria have a large potential to degrade OPs and increase plant growth and ultimately improve phytoremediation efficiency.

- **Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons.**
- **Terpenoids**
- **Humic Substances (Humins)**
- **etc.**

Fig 1. Natural-POPs

How to check the severity of Organic pollutants

The presence of organic pollutants in water are one of the most reliable parameters to check the quality of water. These pollutants have natural or anthropogenic sources. Also there is also a broad spectrum of OP (Organic Pollutants) in municipal, industrial, and agricultural waste water. BOD (Biological Oxygen Density) and COD (Chemical Oxygen Density) are the terms used to determine OP in waste water. BOD and COD check the quantities of chemical and biological oxygen consumed in the oxidation of organic pollutants. On the contrary, the determination of these parameters through customary methods consists of complex procedure, which is time-consuming and reduced detection observance. The conventional procedure needs expensive and unsafe reagent. Likewise, BOM (biodegradable organic matter) is another method that is used to determine the proportion of OP in waste water. BOD is the key parameter for the quantification of BOM of waste water. However, the BOD test requires 5–7 days for the analysis, trained manpower, and careful sampling in conventional systems. Thus, it is essential to use alternative solutions to avoid unnecessary delays due to conventional techniques. Nowadays a rapid detection techniques known as bio sensors came to light and it is appreciably applied in waste water treatment industries. Based upon the principle of photo catalytic and electrochemical theory various bio sensors have been analyzed for waste water observation. These biosensor techniques are proved to be very effective and efficient for observance. On the other hand, Bio- Electrochemical System (BES) based biosensors are more effective and popular in organics detection in waste water. The organic detection in BES is based on a linear relationship between amount of organics and current output. The operational stability of over 5 years has been found in BED-based bio sensors with minimum maintenance. There are three different formulations to be modified in order to determine electrical signals in BES-based biosensors according to Gao et al.

Persistent organic pollutants (POPs) are organic compounds that are resistant to degradation through chemical, biological, and photolytic processes. They are toxic and adversely affect human health and the environment around the world. Because they can be transported by wind and water, most POPs generated in one country can and do affect people and wildlife far from where they are used and released.

The effect of POPs on human and environmental health was discussed, with intention to eliminate or severely restrict their production, by the international community at the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants in 2001.

Most POPs are pesticides or insecticides, and some are also solvents, pharmaceuticals, and industrial chemicals. Although some POPs arise naturally (e.g. from volcanoes), most are man-made. The “dirty dozen” POPs identified by the Stockholm Convention include aldrin, chlordane, dieldrin, endrin, heptachlor,

Fig 2. Classification of persistent organic compounds according to their origin.

HCB, mirex, toxaphene, PCBs, DDT, dioxins, and polychlorinated dibenzofurans. However, there have since been many new POPs added (e.g. PFOS).

Classification of POPs A/C to its Origination

Generally, the origination of POPs are categorized into two heads -
 (1) Natural Origin
 (2) Man-made Origin (Figure 2)

Properties of POP (persistent Organic pollutants)

POPs are either present as vapors in the atmosphere or bound to the surface of solid particles (aerosols). A determining factor for the long-range transport is the fraction of a POP that is adsorbed on aerosols. In adsorbed form it is – as opposed to the gas phase – protected from photo-oxidation, i.e. direct photolysis as well as oxidation by OH radicals or ozone. These have low solubility in water but are easily captured by solid particles, and are soluble in organic fluids (oils, fats, and liquid fuels). POPs are not easily degraded in the environment due to their stability and low decomposition rates. Due to this capacity for long-range transport, POP environmental contamination is extensive, even in areas where POPs have never been used,

and will remain in these environments years after restrictions implemented due to their resistance to degradation.

Career Prospects

It is highly appreciable that any entrepreneur advancing in the field concerned to the green remediation of organic pollutants creates lots of carrier opportunities. Government agencies around the globe used to encourage and promote this endeavor in order to maintain a pollution-free environment. This initiative also assists in the growth of clean and sustainable environment for all. Apart from this, the diseases caused by the widespread use organic pollutants are eliminated and crore of rupees spent on the medication is saved and used in other constructive works. Entrepreneur set up infrastructure for the lessening the ill-effect of organic pollutants. Government supports this initiation with every resource like funding, availing area for establishing set-up.

About the Author

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Artificial POP Examples

- DDT
- PCBs
- Dioxins
- Aldrin
- etc.

Fig 3. Artificial-POPs